

EFFECTIVENESS OF NEURO-LINGUISTIC PROGRAMMING IN HELPING A PERSON

Duisekova Maria Toibekovna

Shymkent University, Shymkent Kazakhstan

Dzhumaev Mamanazar Irgashevich

Professor Tashkent State Pedagogical University after Nizami

Annotation treatment with a Neuro-Linguistic program is widespread. However, this method, like many other information, can be used either to harm themselves, or to the environment. The use of useful or harmful in this direction will depend on the purpose of the application, which will clearly apply the method and method. Therefore, it is always necessary to be responsible for the consequences of using any methods of Neuro-Linguistic Programming.

Negative moments of the use of the described psychotechnics are observed in modern advertising. All advertising propaganda is based on methods of Neuro-Linguistic Programming. At first glance, nothing. However, there is one important "but".

Key words: Neuro-Linguistic Programming, linguistics, language

Neuro-Linguistic Programming is a specific direction of practical psychology and psychotherapy based on the process of copying conscious or unconscious verbal and nonverbal forms of subjects who have achieved success in a particular field. The neuro reflects human thinking, worldview views, and stereotypes based on communication with the environment and society. Followers of Neuro-Linguistic Programming believe that the key to business success is, first of all, the individual, and that the study of the way of thinking allows us to identify the internal resources of a person. Language is a human language, that is, it is an integral part of human life. Initially, people do not think about the importance of speech in a social environment. Understanding language structures and understanding speech structures play an important role in the modern world, where the possibility of communicative interaction is increasingly appreciated.

Programming is when a person manages their personal life using computer-related strategies that use special programs to achieve their goals. learning strategies by regulating their lives, subjects offer you a choice for yourself, whether they work or continue to try to develop their potential and personal effectiveness. In fact, the method of Neuro-Linguistic Programming is the study of their mental activity, behavioral and speech abilities, through which a person can create a set of strategies, building relationships, new initiatives and achievements to facilitate effective decision-making by the management groups of individuals, creating their own existing agreements. A person uses strategy in everything that he does not do. However, often such a strategy exists outside of one's own consciousness. Often actors just don't know why they don't act if they do. Treatment with a neuro-linguistic program is widespread. However, this method, like many other information, can be used either to harm themselves, or to the environment. The use of useful or harmful in this direction will depend on the purpose of the application, which will clearly apply the method and method. Therefore, it is always necessary to be responsible for the consequences of using any methods of Neuro-Linguistic Programming. Negative moments of the use of the described psychotechnics are observed in modern advertising. All advertising propaganda is based on methods of Neuro-Linguistic Programming. At first glance, nothing. However, there is one important "but".

Neuro-linguistic programming methods used for advertising purposes are based on the breakthrough of a logical number barrier and comparisons made by a person when making a

decision to purchase goods. Each subject perceives and reads information coming from the environment differently. Such channels of perception are also called modalities or representative systems. Often in the literature describing different methods of Neuro-Linguistic Programming, there are three channels of perception, i.e. visual or visual, auditory or auditory, sensory or kinesthetic. Through neuro-linguistic programming, you can make changes to the sequence of events that will help you avoid damaging your own psyche. Thus, at the initial stage, a visualization of unpleasant moments for the subject is made, which can be false or real. Neuro-linguistic programming involves intervention in the process of the second stage. It is necessary to imagine that all the visual manifestations of the actions that occurred at the initial stage were thought of by some crazy and funny melody, someone else's cheerful voices. As a result, in the third stage, instead of jealousy, there will be a completely different feeling.

The method of neuro-linguistic programming, as well as other types of psychotherapy, has several limitations. First of all, it is not recommended to use neuro-linguistic programs in politics, since most of the technologies of political manipulation are well known in political society, and attempts to use them immediately indicate the true motives. If a person has set himself the goal of making a career in the legal field, then using the methods of Neuro-Linguistic Programming, he is faced with complete indifference and further exclusion, or with such a strict and purposeful response.

Secondly, for the reasons listed above, the methods of this direction are not used in "big" business. Third, it is not recommended to use the methods of this direction in jurisprudence.

At various stages of the formation of this direction, programmers tried to give it the most accurate definition.

Neuro-Linguistic Programming:

- a science that studies and understands brain codes;
- analysis and reproduction of ideal human behavior;
- a model based on understanding standards of communicative interaction and stereotypes of mental activity;
- training and methodology for the formation of correct methods;
- technology for copying human behavior;
- a set of techniques whose value criteria are their effectiveness.

Neuro-linguistic programming methods are used to improve one's own life and behavioral qualities, improve relationships, career growth, professional implementation, and so on.

Neuro-Linguistic Programming is used in the following areas. Initially, the main area of application of programming is communicative communication of individuals. According to the concept of this direction, human experience includes their feelings and characteristics.

There are no restrictions on what is defined in the theory of Neuro-Linguistic Programming. In addition, the experience of human subjects is considered optimal in comparison with other things. As a result, several applications were born in programming: fears, pain in the trance of management, training of personnel, the study of spiritual experience, the study of behavioral reactions of subjects, improving communication skills, copying the actions of some famous facets to understand patterns of behavior in certain situations.

The technology of neuro-linguistic programming involves the use of various exercises, such as the exercise "film lighting". He lives next. Every person in life has had unpleasant moments. Such memories have a destructive effect on people. To get rid of them, you need to remove the negative image from your memory every time to make it as transparent as possible, until the image is lost.

You can use the described technique and vice versa. For example, a person has forgotten a significant part of the events that need to be restored. For this purpose, each time the story is

presented, it is amplified more and more, in order to make the picture much darker. In this case, the forgotten fragments "come out" of the subconscious. In this way, an individual can take a picture, some elements of which are not allowed. Another effective and well-known exercise in Neuro-Linguistic Programming is called "twenty years later". In order to reduce the intensity of the experience, it is recommended to present negative events or places, for example, this will happen twenty years later.

Treatment with a neurolinguistic program is often used to eliminate alcoholism and phobias. The core of this direction is to achieve the necessary communication (the establishment of trust) to strengthen self – sufficiency, develop charity, kindness, empathy, and improve communication skills. A report can be created by modeling other people's behavioral reactions, such as gestures, poses, facial expressions, scenes, intonation, speech rhythm, and breathing rate.

Proponents in this area help facilitate contacts with the social environment. Eye movement, a person's vision, provides listeners with important information that includes information about their personal vision of receiving information through hearing or feeling.

References

1. Agybaev A. "What causes juvenile delinquency?». Law, No. 5, 2004.
2. Akanov A. A., Zhylkaydarova A. zh. " problems of primary prevention of drug addiction in schools", Valeology and physical education, sports. №2, 2004.
3. Amankulova R. K. "Prevention of adolescent smoking", Valeology and physical education, sports. №1-2, 2005.
4. Baitabanova A. "work of a class teacher with a difficult student", class teacher, No. 4, 2004.
5. Adizova Nigora Bakhtiyorovna. The Arrival of Great, Child and Khan Images in Interesting. European journal of life safety and stability (ejlss). Wwww.ejlss.indexedresearch.org Volume 14, 2022 |
6. Nigora Adizova Baxtiyorovna. 3-4-sinf ona tili darslarida qo'llanadigan tayanch kompetensiyalar. Journal of Advanced Research and Stability. Volume: 02 Issue: 01 | 2022
7. Baxtiyorovna, Adizova Nodira. "Boshlang 'Ich Sinf Ona Tili Va O 'Qish Savodxonligi Darslari Samaradorligini Ta'minlovchi Integratsion Yondashuv Metodikasi." *Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences*. 2023.
8. Adizova, Nodira. "BOSHLANG 'ICH SINIF ONA TILI DARSLARIDA O 'QUVCHILAR NUTQINI O 'STIRISH OMILLARI: XORAZM MA'MUN AKADEMIYASI AX OROTNOMASI." *Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti jurnali* 2.2 (2022).
9. Bakhtiyorovna, A. N., and A. N. Bakhtiyorovna. "The role of oikonyms in microtoponymis of Bukhara district." *Middle European Scientific Bulletin* 4 (2020): 41-43.
10. Amonov U. S., Saparova S. R. The mother tongue textbook of the primary school in elbek's interpretation //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 11. – №. 6. – С. 403-407.
11. Amonov U. S. FOLKLORE IN THE WORKS OF ABDURAUUF FITRAT //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2016. – №. 10. – С. 9-12.
- 12.1. Jumayev R. SADRIDDIN AYNIIY ASARLARIDA AGORONIMLARNING LEKSIK TAHLILI //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). –2023. –Т. 27. –№. 27.
- 13.2. Jumayev R. SADRIDDIN AYNIIY ASARLARIDA TOPONIMLARDAN STILISTIK MAQSADLARDA FOYDALANISH //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). –2023. –Т. 27. – №. 27.
14. Jumayev R. САДРИДДИН АЙНИЙ АСАРЛАРИДАГИ АДАБИЙ (БАДИИЙ) ТОПОНИМЛАР //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). –2023. –Т. 27. –№. 27.
15. Jumayev R. Sadrididdin Ayniy asarlaridagi joy nomlarining tahlili //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). –2022. –Т.23. –№. 23

FEATURES OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE PROCESSES.

Zheldibayeva Aisha Madibekovna

Turkestan region, Shymkent city, Shymkent University

Annotation: *The woman in the company of the priestess was standing a step below him, her lips parted. However, today there are many women who have managed to get into the family and work, become a dear wife, a dear mother, an exemplary daughter-in-law, show themselves in their work, and become an honorable leader. But what is better if a woman is not a politician in power, but a politician in the family?!*

Kazakh women took part in all the affairs of society, except for the upbringing of the younger generation, and expressed their views. He was widely recognized as a wise adviser to Khans and sultans, batyrs and biys. This fact was in the center of attention of researchers of other nationalities

Keywords: *woman, fever, society, dignity, child, mother, respect.*

The meaning of the world is in a woman," Yerman said, adding that in any era, in any people, a woman has a special place. In the Kazakh people, women were considered the song and fashion of life, the warmth of our home, the mind of men, and the caregiver of our children.

A woman is a wise girl, a wise daughter-in-law, a mother, a sister, a sister, a grandmother. A woman has a very responsible task. Nine months and ten days give life to humanity, expanding its narrow belly, soaking up the stone breast. "I don't know," he said. A woman was responsible for the upbringing of her offspring. There is a beautiful saying: "the child should be good." As for its origins, our ancestors paid special attention to the origin and dignity of their mothers and wives. This means that women have a high and responsible place in the process of reproduction.

In the Kazakh society, as well as in our noble religion, the girl was respected, respected and placed above all others. For example, a girl was placed as a guest in her house, a girl was banned from forty houses, the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) considered the child a gift from Allah, preferred the boy, and did not allow discrimination against the girl. After all, the girl's heart is soft, her soul is tender, she explained that tomorrow someone will be a companion, a guest in the right void. Also, in the nomadic farm there were men who raised their shanyrak when building a yurt, women who made a bed, and women who made a bed. Men who saw such advantages in women were protected by various laws. "I don't know," he said. For example: in Dulat Isabekov's story "The Passenger of the lungs", comparing the female substance to an unrecognized planet, scientists from all over the world together reveal the secrets of the world, but no science, genius can reveal the secrets of the female soul.

From an early age, the girl was brought up as a future wife, a dear mother, a white grandmother, as well as household chores, sewing, patchwork, morality, beauty, intelligence, and labor. "A giant is born of a mother," the word has a deep meaning. Almost all of our Khans and biys, brave heroes, poets and writers who ruled the ancient country were born from our mothers with Golden Hearts. The only example of our mothers who raised their children in a wise way is our mothers Domalak Ana, Ulzhan, Umai, Zere, Begim Ana, Shokan's grandmother Ayganym, who are known for their holiness.

Sonau ekinshi duniezhuzilik sogys zamanynda ayelder turli sharualarga aralasy, economy, onerkasip, zhenil onerkasip T.b salalaryn igere bastagan. Sol uakytan bastap aiel adamdar kogamdyk zhumystarga belsene katysyp, aiel adamdarda "er men aiel te kukyly" degen pikirler kalyptas bastady. Eri zhokta esti ayel ony zhoktatpai, barlyk zhumystardy ayel adamdar zhasai beretin darezhege zhetti.

Kazirgi kogamymyzda da ayel adamdardyn orny orasan zor. Ayel adamdardy bassy tulgalar katarynan, bizneste, ekonomikada, sayasatta baska da kasip salalarynda kezdestirip kalatynymyz ras. Olardyn sany kun sayyn artyp keledi desek te, otirik emes. Degenmen, "Altyn basty ayelden,

Baka basty yerkek artyk", - demekshi Alla tagala ayeldi ayel, yerkekti yerkek kylyp zharatkannan keyin, ayel adamdar kansha zherden sharua istep, er adamdarmen te kylymyz